

How the neuroprosthetic hand shapes the embodied perception

Laura Corti
Faculty of Engineering
Campus Bio-Medico University
Roma- Italy
l.corti@unicampus.it

Abstract—The prosthetic limb of today has achieved new functionalities, like the feeling of what is touched and the capacity of precise grasping, since the hook prostheses. We discuss how this replica of significant functions of the human hand implies the concept of embodied perception.

Keywords—neuroprosthesis, embodied perception, sensation

I. INTRODUCTION

How can we describe the relationship between human being and neuroprosthetic limb? It is possible to define it as an embodiment relationship in which the technological device is embedded in the subject and becomes part of the way we perceive the world. The term 'embodiment' is linked with the 'physical' position of the device, implanted in the body, but also with the perceptual function involved.

Therefore, the problem of the embodiment has to be the subject of much systematic investigation. Understanding the complexity of it is vitally important, and the best way is to address the issue in an integrated approach, that comprehends engineering, neuroscientist, psychological and philosophical perspectives.

II. THE CONCEPT OF EMBODIMENT

The term in question means that something becomes part of the body. In the case of prosthetics hand, the question is if a technological device can be perceived not only as a tool able to extend the limits of the physical body but also a part of the self.

The term was coined in the phenomenology, a philosophical inquiry in which the material entity of the body is only a remaining part of the analysis, that is focused on the Leib or living body. The perception is one of the most common topic analysed in phenomenology.

From a functional point of view, it necessary to distinguish two possible dimensions of embodiment: the body image and the body schema. [1]

The body image is describable as the appearance of the human body in the perceptual field, while the body schema is a sensory-motor system that operates autonomously to integrate the body position and the environment. At the same time, a neuroprosthesis is able not only to recreate a complete body appearance but also to shape the perception. The most significant problems are twofold: the design-centred issue concerning the functional and aesthetic questions but also a definition of perception.

In the book *The primacy of movement*, Maxine Sheets-Johnstone introduces a very useful concept, 'kinetic qualia'. "Qualia are 'integral of bodily life'. They are in any movement we make. They are differentially there in the bodily life of animate forms. They are not a mental product but the product of animation. They are created by movement itself." [2] This qualitative aspect can be seen as an essential component of embodiment. This essay aims to investigate the

problem of qualia and relate it with the capability to have feelings through prosthetic hand.

III. THE PROBLEM OF QUALIA

If we want to consider the topic of perception as the ability to have sensation, it is necessary to go beyond functional analysis of embodiment and speak about qualia, plural form of quale, which is a philosophical term connected with the subjective experience. In literature, other expressions describe this concept, as "raw feel" or "what is it like to be" [3]. The main characteristics of this property are: intrinsic, qualitative, subjective, meaningful and not reducible, for an ontological issue, to a physical or neural reaction. Therefore, there is something more that we feel when we have experience.

The best way to describe an untouchable but strong and crucial "feeling" is to refer to a very famous quotation from [4]. Jackson wrote the Knowledge Argument for Qualia. In this hypothetical situation, a brilliant scientist specialised in the neurophysiology of vision, Mary, has always investigated the world "from a black and white room via a black and white television monitor". She acquired all the physical information, and she is able to use qualitative terms, like 'yellow', 'blue'; "she discovers, for example, just which wavelength combinations from the sky stimulate the retina, and exactly how this produces via the central nervous system the contraction of the vocal chords and expulsion of air from the lungs that results in the uttering of the sentence 'The sky is blue'" [4]. Nevertheless, if she goes out or a colour monitor is given, something will happen because, as Jackson said, "It seems just obvious that she will learn something about the world and our visual experience of it. But then is it inescapable that her previous knowledge was incomplete" [4].

In our opinion, Mary has two different kinds of knowledge: the first one is based on an analysis of data, made during the acquisition through television monitor, and the second one is strongly connected with experience, made in the real world, which produces an affective statement. It is not a question of monitor's mediation if the processes of knowledge are different, but it relates to a deeper meaning. In the first case, we have a close system that produces output changing unknown variable; in contrast, the experience opens us not only to a set of data but also to an interaction not predictable that changes the subjective structure; in other words, there is something that Mary feels when she sees the sky for the first time.

To conclude, we do not want to give a judgement, axiologically connoted, but it is fundamental to distinguish the analysis and manipulation of data from experience.

In which ways is it possible to affirm that a patient has qualia through neuroprosthetics? How can we describe it?

IV. THE SENSORIMOTOR ACCOUNT

A possible solution, that we propose in this presentation, is a new theoretical framework, the sensorimotor approach, a philosophical and psychological perspective developed in the

21st century by the philosopher, Alva Noë, and the psychologist, Kevin O'Regan.

In accordance with them, the perception is a complex concept that implies different modalities, like vision, smell, or tasting, that are governed by rules. [5]

How is it possible to provide an explanation of experienced feeling in the sensorimotor approach? Kevin O'Regan identifies four mysteries for raw feeling: it feels like something, that cannot be reduced to a brain function in order to avoid the problem of infinite regress; it has different qualities, for instance, the cold of ice, the sound of piano, the taste of pizza or the redness of red; there is structure in the difference; and, raw feel is ineffable, because it cannot be communicated. These problems are solved in a sensorimotor approach which is based on four characteristics: bodiliness of the experience, richness, partial insubordinateness and grabbiness of the world. According to Kevin O'Regan, the sensorimotor approach can be used to attribute a qualitative statement to products of A.I. because the feeling is strictly integrated on the interaction between agent and environment.

Can we adopt this perspective to describe the ability to recreate the sensation through the prosthetic hand? How does this analysis modify the definition of embodiment?

V. A POSSIBLE EXAMPLE: SQUEEZING A SPONGE

Imagine you are squeezing a sponge and experiencing the feel of softness. What brain mechanism might generate the softness feel? The word generate seems inapplicable here, and so this seems to be the wrong kind of question to ask about softness. Softness is a quality of the interaction you have with a soft object like a sponge. Feeling softness consists in the fact of your currently being in the process of nothing that as you press the sponge, it squishes under your pressure. Having the feeling of softness does not occur in your brain; rather, it resides in your noting that you are currently interacting in a particular way with the sponge" [6].

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